

Design And Fabrication Of Hyperloop

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this review is to explore Hyperloop technology as is used in railway transportation. For many years railways have been playing a significant role in mass passenger and freight transport. In the modern daily travel environment (commuter), railways face new challenges from different perspectives.

Urban railways always focus on how to minimize the vibration and noise from trams, subways and light rail vehicles on the environment.

Intercity transport must focus on how to achieve higher speeds as well as eliminating noise and vibration to minimize travel time and even achieve the potential of diverting passengers from air traffic and decreasing exhaust pollution in the atmosphere.

The Hyperloop, a brand-new transportation concept idealized by Elon Musk. This method may be a proposed mode of transportation that propels a capsule like vehicle through a thermionic valve at more of their airline speed.

Keywords: Hyperloop, Urban railways, Solar, capsule.

1. Introduction

Hyperloop is a proposed high-speed transportation system for both passengers and freight. The concept was documented by Elon Musk in a 2013 white paper, where the hyperloop was described as a transportation system using capsules supported by an air-bearing surface within a low-pressure tube. Hyperloop systems have three essential elements: tubes, pods, and terminals. The tube is a large, sealed low-pressure system (typically a long tunnel). The pod is a coach at atmospheric pressure that experiences low air resistance or friction inside the tube using magnetic propulsion (in the initial design, augmented by a ducted fan). The terminal handles pod arrivals and departures. The hyperloop concept has been promoted by Musk and SpaceX, and other companies or organizations were encouraged to collaborate in developing the technology. A Technical University of Munich hyperloop set a speed record of 463 km/h (288 mph) in July 2019 at the pod design competition hosted by SpaceX in Hawthorne, California.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE JOURNAL

- To design the high-speed prototype car and track for hyper loop by using Catia V5
- To analyze the important parameters like drag force and coefficient of drag by using ANSYS Software and comparing the result with theoretical results.
- To fabricate hyper loop structure for creating the vacuum by using high pressure vacuum
- To calculate the speed with differences, load for different capsule material and different shape

3. SUMMARY OF LITERATURE SURVEY

- The aerodynamic structure where circular shape is more efficient than square surface Improve passenger capacity.
- Station designs with loading and unloading of passenger. Safety features improvement.
- Developing suitable communication system solutions
- Energy storage systems might be used to eliminate the pulsating load characteristics
- The optimizing cost of the Hyperloop system using different seat capacities is dependent on the unit costs
- A speed-oriented approach towards a new era of technology

4. METHODOLOGY

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1
comparison between theoretical and practical values of drag force or different materials

	PVC		GI SHEET		ALUMINUM	
	Theoretical value	Practical value	Theoretical value	Practical value	Theoretical value	Practical value
Drag force	1.2524 N	1.285 N	0.8487 N	0.8794 N	1.214 N	1.255N
Co-efficient of Drag	1	0.62	1	0.699	0.42	0.55

Table 2
speed calculation for different load

Load in g	PVC					
	266 g		366 g		466 g	
	km/h	mile/h	km/h	mile/h	km/h	mile/h
speed	114.65 km/h	71.24 mile/h	90.65 km/h	56.32 mile/h	66.35 km/h	41.22 mile/h

GI SHEET						
Load in g	165 g		265 g		365 g	
	km/h	mile/h	km/h	mile/h	km/h	mile/h
speed	88.17 km/h	54.78 mile/h	72.61 km/h	45.11 mile/h	57.05 km/h	35.44 mile/h

ALUMINIUM						
Load in g	80 g		180 g		280 g	
	km/h	mile/h	km/h	mile/h	km/h	mile/h
speed	123.85 km/h	76.95 mile/h	84.74 km/h	52.65	45.63 km/h	28.35

6. ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT MATERIAL IN ANSYS FLUENT

Fig 1 PVC Particle movement

Fig 1 shows the pressure particle movement over the PVC model. In a hyperloop, air particles move at high speeds within a low-pressure tube, creating minimal air resistance to allow for efficient transportation.

Fig 2 PVC Drag force.

Fig 3 PVC Co-efficient of Drag.

Fig 2 and Fig 3 show the drag force and the co- efficient of drag of model. Check the graph in fig 2 and fig 3, The drag force in a hyperloop model is minimized by maintaining a near-vacuum environment within the tube, reducing air resistance. The coefficient of drag is kept low through streamlined design and smooth surfaces to further optimize efficiency.

ALUMINIUM

Fig 4 Aluminum Particle Movement

Fig 4 shows the pressure particle movement over the Aluminum model. Air particles move within the Hyperloop in a way that is evenly distributed along its two parallel lines.

Fig 5 Aluminum Drag force and Co-efficient of Drag.

Fig 5 shows the drag force and the co- efficient of drag of model. Check the graph in fig 5. The hyperloop model minimizes drag force by maintaining low air pressure within the tube, while its streamlined design reduces the coefficient of drag, enhancing efficiency and speed of travel.

GI SHEET

Fig 6 GI sheet Particle Movement

Fig 6 shows the pressure particle movement over the GI sheet model. Air pressure and particle movement over the flat front surface of a Hyperloop capsule's GI sheet model are evenly distributed, ensuring streamlined airflow and minimal resistance.

Fig 7 Drag force and Co-efficient of Drag.

Fig 7 shows the drag force and the co- efficient of drag of model. Check the graph in fig 7 The drag force acting on the flat front surface of the Hyperloop capsule's GI sheet model is minimized, resulting in a medium coefficient of drag for efficient aerodynamics.

CONCLUSIONS

Comparing the three different materials of model [ALUMINIUM, GI SHEET, PVC] we found that aluminum is faster compared others, has less drag force due to its shape of model.

From the experiment with the three different materials with different length we conclude that decrease in length of the capsule results in higher speed and light weight of the model can travel at a high speed when we increase the power of the vacuum which can travel at a higher speed compared to earlier one.

Air resistance and friction between the capsule and tube reduce and which can travel at high speed. In future the research should be mainly on

- Improvement in Infrastructure Design
- Increase Safety and Security
- Improve in Energy Efficiency
- Research on proper material selection for complete system

7. References

1. Mr.Varun , Faizan Khan , Chuimayo Kapai Arun Kumar , Prajwal G, Design And Development Of Hyperloop Train Volume:02/Issue:03/March-2020 [1]
2. Ingo A. Hansen, Hyperloop Transport Technology Assessment and System Analysis Received 03 Aug 2019, Accepted 03 Aug 2020 (13 Oct 2020)
3. Journal Of Civil & Environmental Engineering, A Review on Hyper Loop Transport Technology Volume 11:7 (11-07-2021)
4. Lambros Mitropoulos, The Hyperloop System and Stakeholders: A Review and Future Directions Submission Received: 3 July 2021 / Revised: 21 July 2021 / Accepted: 22 July 2021 / Published: 28 July 2021
5. Wafa Hedhly, Hyperloop Communications: Challenges, Advances, And Approaches Volume: 2/ Published 19 October 2021
6. Ahmad Tbaileh, Modelling and Impact of Hyperloop Technology On The Electricity Grid Volume: 36, Published 5 September 2021
7. Ingo A. Hansen, Hyperloop Transport Technology Assessment and System Analysis Vol. 43, Published 13 Oct 2020.

8. Konstantinos Gkoumas Michalis Christou, A Triple-Helix Approach for The Assessment of Hyperloop Potential Europe Published: 23 September 2020
9. Max M. J. Openwork and Philip C. Caplan, On the Aerodynamic Design Of The Hyperloop Concept (Massachusetts Institute Of Technology, Cambridge)5-9 June 2017
10. Hamad Almujiabah, Assessing Hyperloop Transport Optimizing Cost with Different Designs of Capsule (Department of Civil Engineering, College of Engineering, Published: 2 March 2023)
11. Indu Khatri, Prabhav, Tarana Singhal, Utkarsh Tiwari, Hyper Loop Transportation System, Bhagwan Mahaveer College of Engineering & Management, Sonipat, India Volume 8, Issue 5, January-2021
12. Kanu Priya, Abdul Naim Khan, D Masroor Alam Ansari, A Comparative Study on Hyper Loop System (School of Engineering and Technology, Jnu, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India) Vol. 7 Received: 13-01-2018; Accepted: 20-02-2018
13. Mark Sakowski, The Next Contender in High-Speed Transport Elon Musk Hyper Loop (University of Illinois at Chicago, Chicago,)
14. Jonas Kristiansen, Evolving Toward a Scalable Hyper Loop Technology (Nøland, Member, Ieee on Vol:9, 9 Dec. 2020)
15. Jonas Kristiansen Nøland, Evolving Toward a Scalable Hyperloop Technology: Vacuum Transport As A Clean Alternative To Short-Haul Flights Vol. 9